

COLONIAL ECONOMY IN THE SOKOTO EASTERN PROVINCE: A CASE STUDY OF ANKA TOWN 1910-1960

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Abstract

This study examines various policies during colonial administrations that affected Anka town in the face of modern infrastructural development and social amenities. Therefore, the paper discusses on the major areas of colonial rule such as infrastructure development, boundary adjustments and disputes, passive resistance against colonial rule and colonial economic policies. The paper also argued that successive Anka rulers' participation greatly contributed to the growth, modernization, and development of the town under review. The paper also emphasized that colonial policies come with amount of maximum exploitations such as the introduction of cash crops, gold mining, and different types of taxation. Above all, the traditional currencies were completely eradicated, hence colonial currencies were the only legal tender.

Introduction

The impact of colonial policies in Anka district affected all development sectors. Although colonial policies in Anka began prior to 1904, infrastructural development such as road constructions began in that year. This was followed in 1906 with boundary adjustment. Both policies, as well as others like the economic was ran concurrently by the provincial government, until the end of colonial rule in 1960. For this discourse these developments are treated according to precedence under separate sections. Accordingly, there are developments that were backlashes of these colonial policies and these are treated in subsequence to the policies that resulted in them. These are boundary disputes and passive resistance which resulted from boundary adjustment.

Development of the colonial infrastructure in Anka

The first sign of colonial presence in Anka was infrastructural development. It became the epoch of colonial administration (Krieger, 1958). The provision of infrastructure became necessary to facilitate the colonial

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interest of exploiting African resources, road construction were all over colonial territories. However, it was as early as 1904, during the reign of Sarkin Zamfara Gado Dan Muhammadu Dan Gibala, 1902-1907, that a plan was drawn to build a new road from Zungeru, the northern colonial headquarters, to Sokoto across Anka. When the project commenced, the level of work reached Daraga in the Kuyambana area when it was suddenly stopped (Krieger, 1958), a situation that resulted in the disuse of the road to Lagos which was linked up with the town of Anka through Bagega. This would have become a major road from Lagos that would link up with the north through southwest Zamfara (Hassan, 2024). It was to pass through Bagega, Anka, and then link up with the Gusau and Jega trunk A road. This road would have also linked up through a series of routes that passed through Bindin, Magami, Dansadau, Gidan Bika and Birnin Gwari to Rijau and eventually down south. The construction of road network during this period also saw the opening of a new road linking Anka with Dangulbi and Dansadau. Subsequently, the building of colonial infrastructures of roads and rail lines continued from this period onward.

Accordingly, these colonial roads were said to have been developed on ancient routes linking Hausaland and some of her neighbors, like the *Kasashen Bauchi* and the Upper Volta region. Subsequently, the major Trunk A road networks of northern Nigeria were developed on the same or along the track of these colonial roads (Bazai, 2024). In 1929, as part of this policy, the growing commercial and semi-urban towns of Gusau and Kaura Namoda were linked to the railway line. The road from Gusau to Jega was also completed and put to use during this period. It is also worth-noting also that the opening of this road from Gusau, in the third decade of the 20th century, complemented activities in the Sokoto and Kebbi axes.

Although the colonial policy of developing road infrastructure can be viewed as primarily for colonial interest it did, positively impact colonized subjects. Socially, it opened up village communication in *Kasar Anka* where the settlement pattern is said to have been in cluster form (Bazai, 2024). These roads were largely maintained through communal efforts under the *aikin gaya*. As previously stated, there were other areas in which the people of Anka came to be affected by other colonial policies during the reign of successive Sarakanan Zamfara in the period under review. One of these was the political sector through boundary adjustment, which was affected in this area by 1907.

Boundary adjustment and disputes in the Anka district

The series of boundary adjustment in Anka district began during the reign of Sarkin Zamfara Abdu Caccabi 1907-1918. In 1907, minor boundary adjustments were undertaken in Sokoto Province as a result of the amalgamation of Borgu and Kontagora provinces. Kaoje, Kuyambana, and Illo were added to the Sokoto Province (Swindell, 1982). As a result of these changes some of the towns that were under Anka district were separated from it and annexed to Bukkuyum, Mafara and Bakura districts, these towns that were transferred to these districts were (a) Bakura district to which Dakko was transferred (b) Kuyambana district newly created, was merged with Bindin and Dangulbi formerly under Anka district (c) Bukuyum district was merged with former Anka district towns of Matsafa (now Masamar Mudi) Gwashi and Adabka (d) Talata Mafara district was merged with some towns under the Anka district, which were Gwaram and Jangebe (Wakili, 2024). These boundary adjustments came with geopolitical changes. This was because all of these towns that were removed from the Anka territory had been under Anka for decades. Merging them with other districts gradually caused dissatisfaction that led to disputes among districts. However, further adjustments of district boundaries continued in the Sokoto province, some of which were down for economic reasons, such as that of the second decade of the twentieth century between Bakura and Mafara on the *nomi jidi* (Wakili, 2024) question.

After the boundary adjustment of 1907-1925 were affected a reassessment of the adjustment was reassessed. This occurred during the reign of Sarkin Zamfara, Ahmadu Barmo 1946-1967. These exercises were conducted in the Anka and Bakura districts. In this adjustment, barayar Zaki was removed from the Anka district and placed under the Bakura district. Consequently, upon these boundary adjustment exercises, many districts felt aggrieved about the whole process. This brought about disputes between districts. Anka was among the districts affected by these disputes.

The boundary adjustment soon resulted in disputes between *Kasar* Anka and some of its neighboring districts. The first of these disputes on boundaries began during the reign of Abdu Cacabi in 1907. This happened when the Sarkin Zamfara Abdu Caccabi and the Sarkin Burmi fought over Dakko. Both claimed that the village was within their territory. In the ensuing disputes, the Sarkin Burmi blamed the geneses of the crisis on one of his men Miko, who was believed to have collaborated with the Sarkin Zamfara. Consequence, Miko was relieved of his position as the village head of Dakko (Shehu, 2001).

On the ascension of Sarkin Zamfara, Muhammadu Katar in 1918, disputes on boundary adjustment that started with the village of Dakko between 1907 and 1918 resurfaced. For this reason, Sarkin Musulmi then, Muhammadu Mai Turare, 1915-1924 ordered the re-assessment of boundaries between disputing districts (Sokoto Native Administration, 1950).

Consequently, among the districts that were accessed by trespassing into territories that were not under them was the Anka district. The Caliph ordered the drawing of a barrier line that would serve as the district boundary. The width was appropriately 30m wide. Stone heap were planted at particular spots as sort of linear points. Furthermore, markings as reference points were made on tree stems to serve as frontier points (Backwell, 1927). Boundary disputes in Sokoto province did not stop in the Anka district. Between 1957 and 1967, the Dansadau district also became immersed in continuous disputes with its neighbor Wasagu. One reason for the disputes involved disagreements over jurisdictional rights between the Sarkin Wasagu in the Kontagora province and the Sarkin Kudun Dansadau of the Sokoto province. Eventually, the district head of Wasagu had to resort to litigation as the persistent row between him and the Sarkin Kudun Dansadau be nowhere to end (Swindell, 1982). Gusau and Kaura Namoda under Sarkin Kiyawa and Sarkin Katsina Gusau, Gidado were also involved in boundary disputes in which the representative of the Sarkin Kiyawa is said to have wrestled some farm lands in Mareri from the inhabitants of Gusau.

Passive resistance to colonialism in Anka

Resistance against colonial rule in Anka district took over forty years to end. This period was from Abdu Caccabi's reign 1902-1907 to the reign of Sarkin Zamfara Ahmadu Barmo 1946-1967. Resistance came in the form of a nonchalant attitude towards colonial orders. This became a continued response to the colonial administration of Sarkaunan Zamfara. The generis of this passive resistance resulted from an unfavorable colonial policy that did not go down well with Anka. This unfavorable policy emanated from the 1907 boundary adjustment with the combination of the provinces of Borgu and Kontagora. In this colonial action minor boundary adjustments were undertaken in the Sokoto province (Wakili, 2024). As a result of these changes, some of the towns that were under the Anka district were separated from it and merged with the districts of Bukkuyum, Mafara and Bakura. Consequently, this action resulted in the Sarkunan Zamfara's change of attitude against colonial rule in Anka. This resistance against colonial rule became so pronounced that by 1911, the colonial administration viewed the district administration in Anka as "one that was characterized by floating of the Native authority order" (McAllister, 1911). A point of reference of this accusation emanated from village units within the Anka district. For instance, the general attitude of the people of Bajoga, a village unit under

Anka, was of sullen indifference to authorities. Orders of the Native authority were not obeyed with the required alacrity. Gradually, this nonchalant attitude of the District Head went beyond flouting the orders of the Native Authority. Even in the census figure conducted in the village, there was a discrepancy between the headman's attitude and that of the residents (McAllister, 1911). However, the difference was not disclosed in the re-assessment report, but item 4 of the report affirmed that it was written under a separate cover. Furthermore, because of the passive response to the native authority orders in Anka between 1907 and 1918, it was deemed to the district officers that Sarkin Zamfara, Abdu Caccabi's problems were not only his slow attitude to duty but he was also unintelligent. This accusation was probably a hoped-for alibi that would trigger official action against the head of the Anka district. His lack of intelligence would render him unfit in his official capacity. However, his reign lasted for 12 years but was full of dissatisfaction on the part of the colonial government. Consequently, by 1918, the people of Bagega, a village unit under him, protested against him and he was dethroned by the Caliph and was banished to Jangebe, where he died (Bazai, 2024).

The problem between the colonial government and the Sarakunan Zamfara did not stop with the dethronement of Abdu Caccabi, it continued into the reign of Sarkin Zamfara Muhammadu Katar, 1918–1931. His twelve year reign was characterized by administrative challenges experienced by the colonial government. The problem went beyond slow alacrity to administrative directives but spilled over to the district's finances. The incidences of misappropriation of public funds became rampant. In a problem, one Yerima was reported to have escaped with 4% of the annual tax generated in the district (Bazai, 2024). Due to the Sarkin Zamfara's passive attitude, Muhammadu Katar lost confidence in his official conduct. In a report to the provincial secretary, the district officer accused the district head of being slow in the dispensation of native authority orders. Consequently, Sarkin Zamfara Muhammadu Katar did not only fail the confidence of the colonial power but also lost their trust. In one of the district officer's report, he was considered prone to corruption and "give one the impression that he would like to dip himself in (district treasury) and grow fat" (Anka District's Headsip, 1946)". This development in the reign of Katar indicated the Sarakunan Zamfara's passive attitude against the Native Authority. He died in 1931 during the reign of Caliph Hassan Dan Mu'azu.

Between 1931 and 1946, the dissatisfaction of the colonial power with the administrations of successive Sarakunan Zamfara continued from Muhammadu Fari 1931-1946, to that of Sarkin Zamfara, Ahmadu Barmo 1946-1967. The British faced these challenges in a form of sublime but passive resistance against colonialism in Anka. Consequently, by 1943 the Sarkin Zamfara, Muhammadu Fari was said to have exhibited complete lack of knowledge or interest in the affairs of his district. In the sensitization of his district on export crop marketing, the district head is said to have been nonchalant, as he neither made an effort in groundnut marketing nor showed a sense of seriousness in his financial expenditure and record keeping. For instance, a road repair whose contract vouchers had already been raised was not paid. According to the district officer's report, the district head's action was not because of non-availability of labour or lack of funds for its purpose but due to his passive attitude to duty (Muazu, 2024). The Anka district Jangali receipts were also improperly handled. Two receipts did not match the actual number of receipts (17). Balance of the account could not be done due to excess entries in the account. The problem of irreconcilable accounts was not only evident in the district but also in the district's records with the Gusau sub-treasury (Anka District's Notebook, 1959).

Apparently, because of the action of the district head, the district officer in Gusau reported that the Sarkin Zamfara had never been successful in his office. By 1946, "Sarkin Zamfara, Muhamamdu Fari was retired from office due to a failing state of health". In a resident's letter in February 1946, he informed the Secretary, Northern provinces that "the district head's health has failed seriously in recent years and periodically attacks of

a painful illness make it impossible for him to attend properly in his duties” (Anka District Assessment Report, 1921)”. The Sarkin Zamfara, Muhamamdu Fari, was commended for his selflessness, as his rule was summed up as “free from personal aggression”. He was recommended for a compassionate allowance for his retirement. He was approved a compassionate allowance on the grounds that he was retiring because his health had seriously failed in recent years. An allowance of 90 pounds per annum with an annual increment of 6 pounds was approved for his retirement (Shehu, 2001). The assessment of his rule as “one unbecoming of an executive officer” who ‘see himself more of a patricidal figure head” further indicated his, disregard for colonial administration. Accordingly, in his official capacity, he had remained a Sarkin Zmafara until his retirement and was not a colonial administrative officer.

Consequently, “his long tenure of office in the fact of the expressed disapproval of successive Caliph and touring officers suggest that his attitude has not been obnoxious to his people” (Umaru, 2024). Sarkin Zamfara Muhamamd Fari retired from office on the 31st of March, 1946.

Colonial resistance in Anka continued after the retirement of Fari in 1946, to the period of Barmo, 1946-1967, Sarkin Zamfara, Ahmadu Barmo 1946-1967, who exhibited no less an attitude in official conduct toward the Native Authority. From the onset, his reign is said to have been nonchalant toward the Native Authority, and he had no respect for his superiors. The colonial officers observed Barmo’s conduct as unsatisfactory, and the touring officers expressed a lack of trust in him. He became the subject of many unfavorable reports by successive touring officers. However, like his predecessors, on the home front, he was popular among his people. This indicates that the continued dissatisfaction in the official conduct of Sarakunan Gusau from 1907 to the reign of Barmo was connected to resistance to colonial rule. This emanated from dissatisfaction with the colonial policy of boundary adjustment, which began in 1907. However, with Nigeria’s independence approach, there was a change in Sarakunan Zamfara’s attitude in their official relations with the Native Authority. At the tail end of Barmo’s reign, he exhibited improved official conduct. His sudden change could not be unconnected with Nigeria’s political developments and its independence. Anka was under his reign when the polls on Nigeria’s independence were conducted.

Colonial Economy in Anka 1903-1960

The economy of Anka from 1903 to 1960. Each of these periods encounter major economic development within it. These were from 1903 to 1931, when export crop production was the major economic activity. Second, the period 1931-1946 witnessed the establishment of European merchant companies in Anka and the commencement of gold mining activity. Third, the period 1946-1955 saw the development of a new form of commerce in the disbursement of company loans through thee *Yan veranda* (Bazai, 2024).

Export crop production

The economy of Anka with the onset of colonial administration in 1903 was geared toward export crop production. Consequently, the district became significant in terms of export crop cultivation owing to its emphasis by the colonial administration. Its significance in export crops was in cotton and sorghum production. Cotton cultivation in the south west Zamfara region became widely practiced by famer not only in Anka but also in the Bukkutum and Gummi district. By 1911, the American long staple variety frown in Bukuyyem district, was said to have been the best variety in northern Nigeria, second only to the Zaria long staple variety. By 1917, the production of export crops in the Anka district had become a source of livelihood for many families (Umaru, 2024).

By 1922, the cotton yield of southwest Zamfara was a subject of colonial interest. On average each farmer produced one hundred Kwando or baskets of cotton and fifty dame or bundle of sorghum at 6 and 3 days on the

spot. However, there was little evidence of wealth either in stock or personal adornment in Anka, during this period. It is said that the people preferred to go about at ordinary times wearing nothing but walk, or leather kilt (Lawal, 1989). The people of this period were rustic and stingy. Within this period, that the cultivation of sugar cane and yam were introduced in Anka. These plants were grown in small quantities and produced good yield. Some crops grown in Anka district by the period, 1911-1922, included both export and domestic crops. Crops grown during this period included sorghum, cassava, tobacco, cotton, indigo, rice, and groundnuts. By 1921, the Anka markets were said to have developed into two double lines of 10m each. Dues accrued from the market amounted to 30 d in the dry season and 15 d in the rainy season. Further developments in this area included the introduction of export crop marketing in Sokoto province, which comprised Anka and forty-four other districts. These were market centers built by the Native Authority for the purchase of specific export crops at government-controlled prices. The centers came up because of the colonial policies on agriculture. Export crop production was encouraged and controlled. By 1931, this development attracted European merchants who came to purchase export crops in the area.

European merchant activities

In Anka, the first presence of European merchant capital was in 1931. In this year, Europeans began to establish their presence in Anka to source raw materials. This influx of European merchants was encouraged by the colonial policy on export crops production. As a policy of the Native Authority, district heads were directed to encourage the production of export crops in their domain. The Sarkin Zamfara Muhammadu Katar encouraged crop production in the Anka district. Owing to his, efforts some commercial development in Anka through export crop sales was boosted. Trade in groundnut and cotton developed to such an extent that European merchant companies began to build ware houses in Anka. John Holt was among the first to open a ware house in 1931 (Lawal, 1989). By this period, European companies must have realized that opening warehouses meant greater access to obtaining raw materials and cutting off the middlemen's activities. This would also improve their profit margins. Consequently, many market centers for the purchase of export crops, such as cotton were established in various districts of the Sokoto province. In 1934, the Dansadau cotton market was opened in Kuyambana district.. Clerks of the United Africa company and Messrs G.B Ollivant lived there and bought 150 tons of cotton in 1938/1939. The Magami cotton market was opened in 1937 (Bazai, 2024).

This colonial period in Anka witnessed some spur of economic activities that later on transformed into further European companies establishing their presence in the town. However, before to the 1930s, the Anka people were said to have been backward and seemed to be content with their lot. During the period 1931-1946, there was no confirmation from any district report or any source to change their earlier account on how commercial activities impacted the people of Anka district.

However, some improvement in the economic development of Anka was observed. This period 1931-1946, coincided with the reign of Sarkin Zamfara Muhammadu Fari. It saw the opening up of more European companies including the United African Company (UAC), G.B Oliviant, London and Kano Trading Company (Lawal, 1989). This was largely due to commercialization in not only export crop procurement and sale but also in other sectors of the economy. The economic endeavors that came up were the purchase of animal hide and skins introduced in Anka after 1931. Europeans called *Turawan ambrosin* began their influx into Anka with this period. These merchants were the hide and skin merchants. Increased the level of commercial transactions in the district. It was also within their period that an important commercial activity in the form of fold mining began in Anka (Umaru, 2024). This mineral exploration caused the 'establishment' of a settlement called "Kamfanin Kuba"

Kueber Firm

One German, believed to have been, a soldier called Kueber (Kuba, the Hausa rendition) (Umaru, 2024), is said to have settled on some high grounds approximately seven kilometers, south-east of Anka during the 1930s. Kueber resided in this uphill house within his wife, daughter Jonnie and dog (Umaru, 2024). He is said to have pioneered mineral exploration activities in the Anka district. Gold mining activities took an earnest start where he settled. However, it is said that the actual prospecting of hold in the Zamfara valley in 1922 by someone called Mr. Roads. By 1932, the land held by companies and individuals for gold mining, especially in the Zamfara valley and Yauri was much. New fields for gold mining began to be worked in the Zamfara area such as Zurmi, Wauni, Maradun, Maru, Danko, and Malele (Umaru, 2024). For more than a decade, during the time Kueber lived in his mine, his activities were restricted around Anka. This occurred during the peak of gold mining and its output in Nigeria 1932-1943. In his theses “Imperial Policy, Capital Accumulation and Gold Mining in Colonial North-western Nigeria 1915-55”, S.U Lawal asserted that export crops and mineral production in northern Nigeria was at a revolutionary phase that followed the extension of the rail lines of 1912. Kueber is said to have mined gold in large quantities during this period. The total gold mined in the period 1932-1943, in this part of Anka, cannot be ascertained. However, the total gold mined in northern Nigeria between 1932 and 1943 showed a great peak against total output within the period 1934-1955. By 1934, 36,380 ounce were mined. By 1935, the gold mined weighed 38,216 ounces. However, the total output of mined fell by 1943, with a drastic amount of 6,538 (Lawal, 1989). This fall in gold mining must have been the reason behind Kueber’s abandonment of the mine in 1959-1960.

However, even when he left gold mining activities continued at the mined field. The continued habitation of the mine site led to the establishment of the thriving village of Kamfanin Kuba (Lawal, 1989). A distance of approximately 200m separate Kueber’s house from the shanty. This shanty transformed into an economically vibrant village called Kamfanin Kuba.

However, it was not only Kueber who made fortunes in the Zamfara valley. Among his miners, some made a great deal out of the gold business. They included, Mahoni, Bawa Fare, Malam Musa, and Kwana. Although they might have made money, some of them must have squandered it in the mine camp. It is said that among the ways of the miners, they seldom left home when they got good finds. They squandered their wealth in high-life activities in the settlement. In the settlement in those days were free women, gambling, alcohol, and music. These unwholesome activities are said to have been encouraged by the mine owners in the 1930s. According to Lawal (1989), “mine owners fostered a culture of gambling, prostitution, and alcoholism in their various camps”. Even today, at the settlement, one finds music, drugs and high-life.

Kueber is said to have left the settlement at the time of Nigeria’s Independence in 1960. Some of his miners are also said to have left after him, whereas others continued with the area’s gold mining activity. Some of the miners who stayed in the area until their death were Malam Musa Bakane, Bawa Fari, Mamman Mai Famfo, (water attendant), Sani Mai Kwamsa, Malam Mai Shukura, and Ba’are. None of them is said to have had a family life in this settlement, but they all lived, worked, and died there. Among the early settlers who still live in the village today is the present village head, Malam Umaru, who was brought to the settlement when he was only nine years old. Today, the Mai Gari is 70 years and presently, there are over 40 household heads in the village. The village has its own Jumuat mosques with Malam Muhammadu as the chief imam. There is a Qur’anic school named Makarantar Malam Yahaya. There is also a nomadic primary school and a cemetery. The ethnic composition of the village is as follows Zamfarawa, Fulbeb, Katsinawa, Sullubawa, Gobirawa, Burmawa, and Adarawa (Umaru, 2024).

Mining activity still occurs around the outskirts of Kamfanin Kuba today. The nature of mining is mainly lode deposit. Miners dug the ground and followed the Gira or the gold deposit trait. Some burrowed pits can reach up to 200 feet below the Earth's crust. The miners usually go into the pit with their waist tied around a rope that is held on the surface by members of their group. Their tools are usually a head lamp, bucket, digger, and a shovel. In Nigeria there are three types of gold deposit; (a) alluvial deposits (b) terrestrial/quartz deposits and (c) lode deposits. Much of the gold mining is said to have been alluvial usually along river beds and banks.

There is still a beehive of activities in the settlement, and many miners are said to arrive on a daily basis looking for fortune. Among the new settlers in the village who came along with their wives in 2013, include Yerima, Malam Gagare, Malam Muhammadu, Isa, and one Bagobiri. These miners came from within and outside Nigeria. Some of the miners that came from Nigeria were Sokoto, Kebbi, and Kano. Those that came from outside Nigeria include countries such as Burkina Faso, South Africa and Niger Republic (Umaru, 2024). These miners still make fortune around Anka gold fields today. The researchers met a young man of about 27 years old named Rabi'u who informed the research that in his not so long stay in Kamfanin Kuba, he had sold raw gold worth six million naira.

Meanwhile, economic policy in the agricultural sector from 1930 -1946 was on export crop production in *kasar* Anka. The increase in cotton production in Sokoto province by 1949 and 1958 doubled (Swindell, 1982). A significant amount was bought by European companies in the area. Many tons of cotton were bought by these companies between 1930 and 1967.

New trading activities

Some new trading arrangement was introduced in Anka district by European company agents between 1946 and 1955. This was when European trading firms introduced the idea of disbursing loans to farmers through a third party in the district. These monies were advanced to a class of businessmen known as *Yan veranda*. In turn the *yan veranda* advanced the monies to cotton export crop farmers who paid back in produce after harvest. However, problems cropped up as some loan beneficiaries could not honor their own part of the bargain. This resulted in the intervention of the court, which prevailed. Some individual loan beneficiaries absconded and were declared wanted (Swindell, 1982).

Crimes committed in Anka emanating from communion with the trading firms did not stop at a breach of trust. Other forms of crimes have also cropped up. These were the incidences of theft usually in the ware house. John Holt's clerk stationed at Anka had 10 bundles of empty sacks stolen by his servant during his absence in 1955 (Danda, 2024). It was claimed that the sacks were sold to the UAC clerk who was also stationed at Anka

The Colonial Currencies

The introduction of new currencies by the colonialists such pounds, shillings and pennies that hitherto replace original currencies such as cowries, iron bars, trade by barter. Therefore, the traditional currencies were completely eradicated, hence colonial currencies were the only legal tender. Thus, colonialists determined the price of local commodities such as cotton, tobacco, groundnut, shea-butter among other export crops. This monopoly gave the colonial masters to purchase large quantities of the above mentioned export crops with small amount of money because they were the custodians of the currencies (Danda, 2024).

Conclusion

Despite many challenges, the colonial administration in Anka survived despite the discontent of some Sarakunan Zamfara. The administrative structures that were established continued to function in independent Nigeria, though with slight modifications. Policies initiated by the colonial government continued to be the

basis of further development in the post-colonial period. However, this was mainly in the agricultural sector in the form of crop export.

Virtually, the economy of the Anka district largely remained agrarian through the production of export crops, especially cotton. Mining, an aspect of the colonial economy, still formed part of the district's economic ventures, especially artisanal gold mining activities. Areas like Bagega, Dareta,, and Kamfanin Kuba are center of the activities. However, European participation in the Anka's economy gradually dissipated after colonial rule. Even lucrative gold mining venture were virtually left to African artisanal miners. On the whole challenges to colonial administration, although pervasive in Anka from 1907-1960 did not hamper the achievement of colonial goals in the areas. Its legacies continue to exist even after colonial rule.

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